

Influence of School Facility Management on History Education Students' Academic Performance in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of school facility management on History Education students' academic performances in Federal University Otuoke (FUO), Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study centered on how school plant management, such as library facilities, classrooms, and teaching laboratories, influences History Education students' performance in FUO. Three research questions guided the study. Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population comprised 400 respondents, drawn from the Department of Foundations, Arts, and Social Science Education (FASSE), Federal University Otuoke. The entire population was adopted as the sample since the population size was manageable. The sampling technique utilized was the census sampling. The instrument for data collection was a researcher structured 12-item questionnaire titled; Influence of School Facility Management on History Education Students' Academic Performance (ISFMHESAP), structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by three experts who are specialists in Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The Chronbach Alpha reliability technique was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument, which yielded a reliability index of 0.79. The study's data were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation while, Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that, library facility management, classroom size, and science laboratory management, significantly predicts History Education students' academic performance. Among other things, the study recommended that the Management of FUO should equip the Faculty of Education with State-of-the-Art Library and Science laboratory facilities in order to enhance students' academic performance in the state.

Keywords: School Facilities, Management, Science Laboratory, Students' Academic Performance.

Introduction

Across the globe, it has been unequivocally ascertained that education serves as the fundamental cornerstone upon which society's progress and advancement are built. Education serves as the bedrock for the progression of technology, the acquisition of skills, the cultivation of literacy, and the indispensable instrument for harnessing both human and material resources. For any nation to thrive and progress swiftly, it is crucial to prioritize the quality of its education system. Education holds paramount importance for nations around the world, and Nigeria is no exception. Ngarbarara

(2019) described education as a major instrument for tackling unemployment, poverty and ignorance. It is a multifaceted endeavour wherein, individuals cultivate and enhance their aptitudes, capacities, and skills. The aptitudes, capacities, and skills encompass a wide array of physical, social, emotional, and intellectual domains. Due to the global significance of education, primary and secondary educational institutions in Bayelsa State, as well as Nigeria as a whole, have witnessed a consistent upward trend in annual enrollment. As a result, additional educational institutions have been established. As anticipated, the increase in enrollment has placed a substantial burden on the current educational infrastructure, resulting in significant ramifications for students' academic achievements.

According to Okafor (2010), the insufficiency of school infrastructure poses a significant obstacle to students' academic performance in Nigeria. Ehiemetolor (2001) stated that the school plant serves as the operational input for every educational program. Furthermore, as posited by Akpan (2003), the amalgamation of the school plant encompasses the environment, equipment, facilities, and buildings. To promote the optimal comfort and welfare of both educators and learners, modern educational establishments require suitable spaces for classrooms, libraries, recreational amenities, assembly halls, standard sickbays, school farms, staff rooms, offices, and other related amenities. The status, adequacy, quality, and relevance of the school's facilities immediately affects how engaged students are in their learning process. According to Mgbodile (2004), the elucidation of the school plant refers to the tangible embodiment of educational initiatives and undertakings. In a deliberately orchestrated and meticulously governed environment, the primary goal is to effectively facilitate the achievement of educational objectives within the institution.

As per the scholarly work of Oyelewe (2010), it is of utmost importance to acknowledge the intricate interconnection and interdependence between the school environment and educational objectives to foster optimal teaching and learning outcomes. In addition to providing a protective barrier against environmental factors such as solar radiation, rainfall, and moisture, the presence of school vegetation exerts a substantial impact on the overall welfare and safety of all individuals within the confines of the educational institution. The educational milieu's fundamental objective is to foster an environment conducive to the cultivation of ideal circumstances that facilitate effective pedagogy and knowledge acquisition. Given the profound influence that educational infrastructure has on students' academic performance, provision, management, and maintenance must be approached with the utmost gravity. Administrators of tertiary institutions bear a shared responsibility for the effective administration of educational infrastructure. The educator plays a critical role in imparting knowledge to students regarding the appropriate use of educational facilities and curriculum implementation.

Due to a prevailing culture of insufficient upkeep, a significant proportion of tertiary institutions endure a myriad of predicaments, including but not limited to deteriorated edifices, shattered glass panes, deficient or non-existent recreational amenities, and roofs that exhibit leakage (Mbot, 2002). A first assessment that included touring a carefully selected range of tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State corroborated this. Unfortunately, this situation is linked to below-average academic performance among students. Upon scrutinizing the universities in Bayelsa State, one cannot help

but discern a prevailing ambience of despondency, a dearth of resources and apparatus, and a culture characterized by substandard maintenance.

In FUO, adequate management of facilities such as libraries, classrooms, and laboratories is essential for creating a conducive learning environment that fosters academic success. In a context where educational resources are often limited, studying the specific influence of facility management on student performance is essential for informing policy decisions and resource allocation. This research aims to provide empirical evidence on how effectively managed school facilities contribute to improved academic performance, thereby highlighting areas where interventions may be needed to optimize educational outcomes for History Education students at the university. There is insufficient empirical research to definitively determine the connection between school infrastructure management and students' academic performance in Federal University Otuoke hence, the study.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the increasing recognition of the importance of educational infrastructure in promoting academic success, many universities in Nigeria, including Federal University Otuoke, face challenges related to the effective management of school facilities. Inadequate or poorly maintained facilities, such as overcrowded classrooms, under-equipped libraries, and outdated laboratories, can hinder the learning process, leading to suboptimal academic performance among students. History Education students, who require specific resources for effective learning and research, are particularly vulnerable to these challenges. The lack of empirical studies exploring the direct impact of school facility management on academic outcomes in this context creates a gap in the literature and impedes efforts to develop targeted interventions.

This study sought to address this gap by investigating the influence of school facility management on the academic performance of History Education students at Federal University Otuoke. By systematically analyzing how the management of key facilities correlates with students' academic performance, this research provided actionable submissions that can inform policy and practice. The findings highlighted critical areas where improvements in facility management could lead to significant enhancements in student performance, thereby contributing to the broader goal of improving educational quality and outcomes in Nigerian universities.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the research was to ascertain the influence of school facility management on History Education students' academic performance in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Specifically, the study determined:

1. the relationship between management of library facilities and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.
2. the relationship between management of classroom size and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

3. the relationship between management of science laboratory and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between management of library facilities and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?
2. What is the relationship between management of classroom size and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?
3. What is the relationship between management of science laboratory and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha.

1. There is no significant relationship between management of library facilities and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.
2. There is no significant relationship between management of classroom size and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.
3. There is no significant relationship between management of science laboratory and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

Methods

The research adopted the descriptive survey design. This was considered appropriate for this study because it allows for the systematic collection of data from a large population of History Education students at Federal University Otuoke to determine the current status of school facility management and its influence on academic performance. According to Creswell and Creswell (2023), descriptive surveys are effective for capturing and quantifying attitudes, behaviors, and conditions as they exist in a particular context, making them ideal for educational research where understanding the current situation is critical for developing informed interventions. Additionally, the descriptive survey design is supported by recent studies that highlight its suitability for exploring relationships between variables in educational settings. For instance, Kumar (2022) emphasized that descriptive surveys are particularly useful when the research objective is to identify trends, correlations, and patterns within a population. This design allowed for the collection of quantifiable data that can be statistically analyzed to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between school facility management and academic performance.

The population of the study comprised of 400 respondents, drawn from the Department of Foundations, Arts, and Social Science Education (FASSE), Federal University Otuoke. The entire population was adopted as the sample since, the population size was manageable. The sample comprised of 156 students from 100L, 120 students from 200L, 64 students from 300L, and 60 students from 400L, making a total of 400 respondents. The sampling technique utilized was the census sampling. The instrument for data collection was a researcher structured 12-item questionnaire titled; Influence of School Facility Management on History Education Students'

Academic Performance (ISFMHESAP), structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by three experts who are specialists in Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The Chronbach Alpha reliability technique was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument, which yielded a reliability index of 0.79. The study's data were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation while, Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any mean score equal or higher than the criterion mean score of 2.5 is accepted to have a positive influence on students' performance otherwise, negative.

Result

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between management of library facilities and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of relationship management of between library facilities and History Education students' academic performance.

SN	Items	N	Mean	STD
1.	Managing students' activities in a functional library enhance the educational success of History Education students' academic performance?	400	3.5	1.2
2.	How much does the management and furnishing of library enhance the educational performance of History Education students?	400	3.7	1.1
3.	To what degree does a good Library with current and up to date reading materials with latest information enhance the academic performance of History Education students?	400	3.6	1.3
4.	To what degree does provision of good e-library facility boost confidence and academic performance of History Education students?	400	3.8	1.0
Grand		400	3.65	1.15

The four items presented to address research question one in Table 1 yielded mean scores of 3.5, 3.7, 3.6, and 3.8, each exceeding the criterion mean of 2.5. These results suggest that having a functional e-library, equipping the library with current and up-to-date materials, and ensuring proper management of the library are significant factors contributing to the high academic performance of History Education students. Furthermore, the grand mean of 3.65 reinforced that the participants agreed on the direct influence of library facility management on History Education students' academic performance.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between management of classroom size and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of relationship between management of classroom size and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

SN	Items	N	Mean	STD
1.	To what extent does planning physical learning space influence History Education students' academic performance?	400	3.20	1.4

2.	How much does a well-designed classroom size encourage feeling, provide a sense of security, and help History Education students learn more effectively?	400	3.70	1.1
3.	To what extent does architectural and other features of learning space influence students' educational performance?	400	3.52	1.3
4.	To what extent does poor acoustic, poor ventilation, insufficient lighting and chronic noise exposure influence students' academic performance?	400	3.84	1.2
Grand		400	3.57	1.25

Table 2 showed four items analyzed to address research question two. The recorded mean scores of 3.20, 3.70, 3.52, and 3.84, all surpassed the criterion mean of 2.5. This indicated that aspects such as planning physical learning spaces, designing appropriate classroom sizes, and incorporating effective architectural features, significantly contribute to the educational success of History Education students. Additionally, the grand mean of 3.52 reflected that participants concur that well-managed classroom sizes positively influence the academic performance of History Education students.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between the science laboratory and History Education students' academic performance in FUO?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the relationship between management of Teaching laboratory and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

SN	Items	N	Mean	STD
1	To what extent does planning of laboratory practical influence History Education students' academic performance?	400	3.72	1.3
2	How much does planning and managing science laboratory inputs/chemicals influence History Education students' academic performance?	400	3.90	1.0
3	To what extent does good science laboratory technologist who assist in the process of carrying out effective science experiment influence History Education students' academic performance?	400	3.71	1.2

4	To what extent does first- hand experience in observation and manipulation of science method influence History Education students’ academic performance?	400	3.81	1.0
Grand		400	3.79	1.13

Table 3 revealed that the four items addressed in research question three, yielded mean scores of 3.72, 3.90, 3.71, and 3.81, all exceeding the criterion mean of 2.5. These results suggest that effective planning of laboratory practicals, proper management of science laboratory inputs and chemicals, and the assistance of a science laboratory technologist are crucial factors influencing the academic performance of History Education students. Furthermore, the grand mean of 3.79 indicated that participants all agreed on the direct positive impact of science laboratory management on the academic performance of History Education students.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the management of library facilities and History Education students’ academic performance in FUO.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis for Library Facilities and History Education Students’ Academic Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Si g.
(Constant)	50.123	4.567		10.975	.000
Library Facility	0.450	0.065	0.440	6.923	.000

R: 0.440, R²: 0.194, Adjusted R²: 0.192, F-statistic: 47.916, p-value: .000

The multiple regression analysis in Table 4 showed that library facility management significantly predicts students’ academic performance (B = 0.450, t = 6.923, p < 0.05). The R² value of 0.194 indicates that approximately 19.4% of the variance in academic performance is explained by the management of library facilities. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between classroom size and History Education students’ academic performance in FUO.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis for Classroom Size and History Education Students’ Academic Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Si g.
(Constant)	52.678	5.112		10.303	.000
Classroom Size	0.360	0.078	0.335	4.615	.000

R: 0.335, R²: 0.112, Adjusted R²: 0.110, F-statistic: 21.301, p-value: .000

The multiple regression analysis in Table 5 indicated that classroom size significantly influences students' academic performance ($B = 0.360$, $t = 4.615$, $p < 0.05$). The R^2 value of 0.112 showed that 11.2% of the variance in academic performance is accounted for by classroom size management. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between science laboratory management and History Education students' academic performance in FUO.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis for Science Laboratory and History Education Students' Academic Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Si g.
(Constant)	48.312	5.234		9.230	.000
Science Laboratory	0.276	0.091	0.276	3.033	.003

R: 0.276, **R²:** 0.076, **Adjusted R²:** 0.074, **F-statistic:** 9.199, **-value:** .003

The multiple regression analysis in Table 6 revealed that science laboratory management significantly predicts students' academic performance ($B = 0.276$, $t = 3.033$, $p < 0.05$). The R^2 value of 0.076 implies that 7.6% of the variation in academic performance can be attributed to the management of science laboratories. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

Relationship Between Management of Library Facilities and History Education Students' Academic Performance

The findings indicated a significant positive relationship between the management of library facilities and the academic performance of History Education students. The mean scores for items related to library functionality, currency of materials, and e-library facilities all exceeded the criterion mean, with a grand mean of 3.65, signifying strong agreement among participants on the positive influence of effective library management. This suggests that well-managed libraries, equipped with current resources and functional e-library systems, significantly contribute to enhanced academic outcomes.

Supporting these findings, Mdodana-Zide (2024) emphasized that access to well-resourced libraries positively affects student engagement and academic performance. Similarly, Ngera et al. (2023) found that the quality and management of library resources play a crucial role in developing students' critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and overall academic success. Estrada et al. (2023) also highlight that high-quality library services enhance students' comprehension and research capabilities, further reinforcing the critical role of library management in academic achievement. Additionally, Samo et al. (2024) noted that comprehensive library support contributes to higher levels of student well-being, indicating that optimized library resources have broader benefits beyond academic performance. Liu (2023) further supported this by linking improvements in library management to positive influence on college students' mental health and

personality development, underpinning the extensive benefits of well-managed library facilities for student growth and welfare.

The Relationship Between Management of Classroom Size and History Education Students' Academic Performance

The results revealed that the management of classroom size has a positive impact on the academic performance of History Education students. Mean scores for items related to classroom size and design exceeded the criterion mean, with a grand mean of 3.57 indicating that appropriate planning and management of classroom environments significantly contribute to students' educational success. This aligns with findings by Ye (2024) and Palm (2024), who highlighted the critical role of classroom environment and size in enhancing students' learning and engagements. These studies underscore how a positive classroom setting, which includes well-designed spaces and supportive teaching practices, can greatly influence students' motivation, collaboration, and overall academic performance.

Supporting this, López-Chao et al. (2020) provided evidence that well-managed classroom spaces with optimal sizes improve student outcomes, reinforcing the importance of effective classroom management in educational success. Additionally, Earthman (2024) demonstrated that the physical management of learning environments is crucial for academic performance, further validating the significance of classroom size and design in fostering a conducive learning atmosphere. These findings collectively emphasized that strategic management of classroom spaces is essential for maximizing student performance and creating an effective learning environment.

The Relationship Between Science Laboratory Management and History Education Students' Academic Performance

The analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between the management of science laboratories and the academic performance of History Education students. With mean scores for all items exceeding the criterion mean and a grand mean of 3.79, the results suggest that effective planning and management of laboratory resources are crucial for enhancing student performance. Mohzana et al. (2023) support these findings, noting that well-managed science laboratories are essential for facilitating effective learning and skill development. Their research highlights that proper laboratory management not only enhances students' practical skills but also significantly impacts their academic success.

Similarly, Setiya Rini et al. (2024) emphasize the importance of effective management of laboratory resources and the role of laboratory staff in influencing students' practical skills and academic achievements. Their study underscores that well-organized and resource-rich laboratory environments contribute to improved student outcomes. Additionally, Mohzana et al. (2023) further validate that hands-on laboratory experiences and their effective management are critical in enhancing educational outcomes in science disciplines. These findings collectively underscore the pivotal role of science laboratory management in supporting student performance and achieving academic excellence.

Conclusion

The study provided compelling evidences that the management of educational facilities—namely library resources, classroom sizes, and science laboratories—plays a crucial role in influencing the academic performance of History Education students at Federal University Otuoke. The findings emphasized that well-managed library facilities, including functional e-libraries and current materials, significantly enhance students' academic performance. Similarly, the study highlights the importance of appropriate classroom size and design in fostering a conducive learning environment that supports student engagement and performance. Furthermore, the effective management of science laboratories, encompassing resource planning and practical support, is shown to be critical for improving students' hands-on skills and overall academic performance. These results aligned with recent research demonstrating that optimized management of educational resources contributes to higher academic outcomes and better student well-being. By addressing the key elements of library management, classroom design, and laboratory resources, this study provided valuable information into how institutional practices can be improved to support student success. Moving forward, educational institutions should prioritize these areas to create more effective learning environments that enhance student performance and foster academic excellence.

Recommendations

Following the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Management of FUO should equip the Faculty of Education with State-of-the-Art Library and Science laboratory facilities in order to enhance students' academic performance in the state.
2. Federal University Otuoke should invest in updating and expanding library resources, including both physical and digital materials.
3. The university should prioritize the design and maintenance of classrooms to ensure they are conducive to learning. This includes considering optimal classroom sizes, adequate ventilation, lighting, and acoustic conditions.
4. The university administration should establish a system for the continuous monitoring and evaluation of the management practices of all educational facilities.

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